

Participation of Women in Yam Production Among Farmers in Enugu and Ebonyi States, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study surveyed the participation of women in yam production among women in Enugu and Ebonyi States in South East Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the socio economics characteristics of the respondents; identified the improved yam technologies used by respondents; assessed the level of participation of women in yam production; identified the constraints in yam production among women in the study area and examined the effects of socio economic factors on yam production among women in the study area. This study was carried out in South-East, Nigeria. The study population constituted women yam producers in Enugu and Ebonyi States in South-East, Nigeria. The sampling size of the study was one hundred and twenty (120) respondents. Primary data were collected using questionnaire and analysis was done using descriptive and inferential statistics. The highest proportion (33.33%) and (35.00%) of the respondents were within the age range of 50-59 years and 30-39 years. Majority (85.00%) of the respondents were aware of improved yam varieties in the study area. The most common improved yam production technology practice used by the respondents was organic manure, the common improved yam planted by the respondents were; white yam (95.00% and 85.00%), yellow yam (88.33% and 71.67%), Aerial yam (80.00% and 66.67%), Water yam (75.00% and 63.33%). The grand mean of the level of participation of women in yam production in the study area was 2.79 and 2.82 respectively. The most constraints to yam production included: fragmentation of land, Poor access to credit, climate change, unavailability of finance and storage facilities, lack of fertilizer. However, household size, education, income and farm size exerted significant effect on yam production in the study area. The study recommended that government should aim at solving the major constraints of farmers especially in facilitating access to loans to aid production, making needed inputs available in time and at subsidized rate and deployment of experienced extension workers to aid the farmers.

Keywords: Survey, Participation, Women, Yam, Production.

INTRODUCTION

Yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) is an annual or perennial tuber-bearing plant, a tropical crop with many species, out of which six are economically important in terms of food and medicine (IITA, 2009). Yam originated in South East Asia and was brought to West Africa in the 16th century. It is one of the principal tuber crops in the Nigeria economy. Nigeria is the leading world producer accounted for over 65% of world yam annually, producing an average of 38 million metric tons (Odinwaetal 2016). Yam is an important source of carbohydrate for many people of the Sub Saharan region especially in the yam zones of West Africa. It's the second most important tuber crop in Africa, after cassava, with production reaching above one third of the level of cassava (FAO, 2002). Yam tuber is essentially a starchy food, its principal nutritional function being the supply of calories to the body (Onwueme, 2001). Nigeria accounted for over 65% of world yam annually producing an average of 38 million metric tons (Odinwa et al ,2016).

Yam is regarded as men crop in the southeast zone of Nigeria, which may be practically true or not, Women are playing a larger role in yam production in some parts of Nigeria. More women are participating in yam production and processing, but with limited access to resources (Kathryn *et al* ,2012). Observations had shown that both men and women plant yam

in most part of Nigeria, and women even grow yam more than men in some areas where men engage in drinking of palm wine. In parts of southeastern Nigeria, men and women combine efforts to do the planting; the women carry out weeding about 2-3 times before harvest; and men and women combine efforts again at crop maturity to harvest and even processing (Kathryn *et al*, 2012). Industrial processing and utilization of yam includes starch, livestock feed, flour and pounded yam flour, yam balls, yam chips, Traditionally, the processing of pounded yam using pestle and mortar is highly valued but is gradually being replaced in the market with instant-pounded yam flour, currently, yam is commonly processed into varying forms such as yam flour, pouno yam flour, flakes, and other value added products. Processed yam can be easily stored for a long period (12 - 18 months) (Komolafe and Akinoso ,2005; Salawu, *et al*, 2014). Yam is commonly processed into varying form such as yam chips, flour, pouno yam flour, flakes, balls.

Despite high women's involvement in yam production, women experience greater constraints in accessing production resources. (Kathryn *et al*,2012). Participation of women in most root and tuber crops production cannot be over emphasized such as cassava sweet potato, etc. It is good to find out the level of women involvement on yam production for reference purpose.

Objectives of the study

1. Examine the socio economics characteristics of the respondents.
2. Identify the improved yam technologies used by respondents.
3. Identify the improved yam cultivars used by respondents.
4. Assess the level of participation of women in yam production
5. Identify the constraints in yam production among women in the study area.
6. Examine the effect of socio economic factors on yam production among women in the study area.

Methodology

Study area

This study was carried out in Enugu and Ebonyi located in South-East, Nigeria. The area is lying on latitude 5⁰ and 7⁰ 75` North and longitude 6⁰ 85` and 8⁰ 46` East. South-East Nigeria is one of the six geo-political zones in Nigeria (North-West, North-East, North- Central, South-West, South-East and South-South) and it comprises of five states: Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States. It has a rural population density of 173 persons per square kilometre. The area lies mainly on the plains under 200m above sea level, covering a total land area of about 109,524 square kilometres or 11.86% of the total land area of Nigeria (NPC, 2006).

The South-easterners are predominantly agrarian. Major crops cultivated include maize, rice, melon, yam, root and tuber crops as well as vegetables while major animals reared include poultry, sheep and goat, rabbits, pigs, snails while they also engage in such activities as fish farming and bee-keeping. The climate of the southeast can be generally described as tropical with two distinct seasons; wet and dry seasons with average highest annual rainfall at 19.52mm and temperature pattern-mean daily and annual temperature at 28 and 27°C, respectively (Igbokwe *et al*, 2008).

Sampling techniques

The study population constitutes yam producers in South-East, Nigeria and the sampling size of the study was one hundred and twenty (120) respondents. In order to obtain a representative sample, the study made use of a multistage sampling technique to select respondents. In the first stage, two states (Enugu and Ebonyi) were selected purposively out of the five states making up South East Nigeria for the reason of availability of large number of women yam farmers. In the second stage, three Local Government Areas namely: Animi, Agwu and Nkanu West were purposively selected from Enugu State for the reason of large number of yam farmers in the zones. Also, three Local Government Areas namely, Abakiliki, Ivo and Ikwo were purposively selected from Ebonyi State for the reasons of availability of large number of yam farmers.

In the third stage, two communities were randomly selected from the selected L. GAs. This gave a total of twelve (12) communities for the study. A list of all women yam producers and processors in the selected communities were obtained from the key informants, extension agents and community leaders in the area, which formed the sampling frame of the study. From the frame, ten (10) yam women farmers were randomly selected for the study which gave a total of one hundred and twenty (120) respondents for the study.

Data collection

Primary data were collected using a questionnaire. The questionnaires were designed to elicit information from the respondents. The questionnaires were administered to yam producers only

Data Analysis

In pursuance of the objectives of the study, various econometric and statistical tools were applied as deemed suitable for the study. Objectives one was realized using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, percentages and cross tabulation was objective two, three, four, five and six were realized with four point Likert type and was analyzed with mean rating. Objective six and seven were realized using multiple regression analysis.

Model specification

Objective two, three, four, five and six were realized with 4-point Likert type adapted from Iheke (2016). Where: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4; Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1. Therefore, the Likert mean

$$= \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = 2.5$$

The mean response was calculated as follows:

$$CS = \Sigma X/N$$

Where

X = Weight on scale

N = Total number of weights

The mean score of each question was computed by multiplying the total number of responses for a particular question with the weight attached to the response chosen and then divided by the total number of respondents.

The decision rule was that any variable or factor with $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ was regarded as significant while the factor or variable with $\bar{X} < 2.5$ was not significant. As such a mean score of 2.5 and above was adjudged very high level, 2.0-2.4 was adjudged high level, 1.5-1.9 was adjudged low level, and below 1.5 very low level.

Objective seven was analyzed with multiple regression model. Four functional forms of the models namely linear, exponential, semi-log and double log were fitted.

The model was specified implicitly as follows:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, X_9, X_{10}, X_{11})$$

Where:

Y = Yam production (t/ha)

X₁ = Age (Years)

X₂ = Sex (Male=0, Female=1)

X₃ = Marital status (1=married, 0= otherwise)

X₄ = Household size (Number of persons)

X₅ = Education (Number of years spent in school)

X₆ = Income (Naira)

X₇ = Farming experience (Years)

X₈ = Cooperative membership (1=yes, otherwise=0)

X₉ = Farm size (Ha)

β₀ = Intercept

β₁- β₉ = Parameter estimate

e_i = Stochastic variables or error term

Results and discussion

The socio economic characteristics of the respondents are presented in table 1. These characteristics include sex, age, marital status, educational status, work experience, household size, primary occupation, social group, access to credit and income.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to socio economic characteristics

Variables	Enugu State (n= 60)		Ebonyi State (n =60)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Age				
< 20	0	0.00	1	1.67
20-29	5	8.33	5	8.33
30-39	18	30.00	21	35.00
40-49	9	15.00	12	20.00
50-59	20	33.33	15	25.00
Above 60	8	13.34	6	10.00
Total	60	100	60	100
Mean	46		42	
Marital status				
Single	9	15.00	24	40.00
Married	51	85.00	36	60.00
Total	60	100	60	100
Education				
None	4	6.70	0	0.00
Primary	28	46.70	24	40.00
Secondary	26	43.30	35	58.30
Tertiary	2	3.30	1	1.70
Total	60	100	60	100
Farming experience				
<10	10	16.67	10	16.67
10-19	20	33.33	23	38.33
20-29	15	25.00	13	21.67
30-39	15	25.00	14	23.33
Total	60	100	60	100
Mean	20.1		19.8	
Household size				
< 3	0	0.00	1	1.67
3-6	27	45.00	47	78.33
7-10	31	51.67	11	18.33
Above 10	2	3.33	1	1.67
Total	60	100	60	100
Mean	6.8		5.3	
Farm size				
< 1	34	56.67	32	53.33
1-2	13	21.67	8	13.33
3-4	10	16.66	14	23.34
Above 4	3	5.00	6	10.00
Total	60	100	60	100
Mean	1.6		1.9	

Source field Survey, 2021

Result in Table 1 showed that the highest proportion (33.33%) of the respondents in Enugu State were within the age range of 50-59 years whereas most (35.00%) of the respondents Ebonyi State were within the age range of 30-39 years. However, the mean age of the respondents in Enugu State and Ebonyi State were 46 and 42 years respectively, implying that are middle aged, experienced and productive. This result is in agreement with Okeke and Udeora (2013) who reported yam farmers in Anambra State were between the ages of 46 and 60 years. Majority (85.00%) of the respondents

in Enugu State were married while 15.00% of them were single. On the other hand, majority (60.00%) of the respondents in Ebonyi State were married while (40.00%) of them were single. This finding reveals that greater proportion of respondents in Enugu State and Ebonyi State were married, this finding is in tandem with Ufondu, Maziya-Dixon, Okonkwo and Okoyeuzu (2021) who reported that married women dominated yam production and processing business in Ebonyi State. The highest fraction (46.70%) of the respondents in Enugu State attended primary school while majority (58.30%) of the respondents in Ebonyi State have attended secondary school. Following the findings, the respondents in Enugu State and Ebonyi State could be said to be literate since the majority attended formal education. Access to formal education to a large extent could determine the respondent's level of adoption of new agricultural innovations without difficulties which might in turn increase their farm output and subsequently the profit obtained by the farmers. Most (33.33) of the respondents in Enugu State had farming experience of 10-19 years while the highest fraction (38.33) of the respondents in Ebonyi State had farming experience of 10-19 years. On the average, the farming experience of the respondents in Enugu State and Ebonyi State were 20.1 years and 19.8 years respectively. Ameh and Iheanacho (2017) reported that increase in the years of farming experience leads to farmer ability to manage, operate a farm and increase in the output. These long years of farming experiences support the findings that older people were engaged in small-scale yam farming in the study areas.

Majority (51.67%) of the respondents in Enugu State had household size of 7-10 persons while the most (78.33%) of the respondents in Ebonyi State had household size of 3-6 persons. On the average, the household size of the respondents in Enugu State and Ebonyi State were 6.8 persons and 5.3 persons respectively. This result revealed that the respondents maintained a relatively sizeable household which could serve as insurance against shortfalls in labour supply and a source of cheap labour. This finding is in line with Ufondu, *et al.*, (2021) who reported that women farmers in Ebonyi State maintained household size of 6-10 persons. The farm size of majority (56.67%) of the respondents in Enugu State was less than 1ha hectare while the respondents in Ebonyi State also had farm size of less than 1ha. On the average, the farm size of the respondents in Enugu State and Ebonyi State were 1.6ha and 1.9ha respectively. This result implies that majority of the respondents are marginal farmers because the cultivated less than 1ha of land. This finding is in agreement with Ufondu *et al.*, (2021) who reported that yam farmers in Ebonyi State cultivated less than 2ha of land.

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents according to the use of improved yam technologies

Awareness	Enugu State (n= 60)		Ebonyi State (n =60)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	42	70.00	51	85.00
No	18	30.00	9	15.00
Total	60	100	60	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

Table 2 ascertained farmers' awareness and use of improved yam practices in the study. About 70.00% of the respondents in Enugu State are aware of the improve yam practices. Also, 85.00% of the respondents in Ebonyi state are aware of improved yam practices. The preponderance of the respondents with awareness of improved yam production practices could be attributed to cooperative membership, educational level as well as access to extension services in the study areas.

Table 3: The distribution of the respondents according to the yam technologies used

Indicators	Enugu State (n= 60)			Ebonyi State (n =60)		
	Frequency*	Percentage	Rank	Frequency*	Percentage	Rank
Inorganic fertilizer	35	58.33	6 th	47	78.33	2 nd
Improved variety	52	86.67	2 nd	41	68.33	4 th
Pesticide	20	33.33	8 th	14	23.33	8 th
Herbicide	31	51.67	7 th	40	66.00	5 th
Organic manure	58	96.67	1 st	55	91.67	1 st
Minisett	39	65.00	4 th	43	71.67	3 rd
Seed yam	40	66.67	3 rd	31	51.67	7 th
Ware yam	37	61.67	5 th	34	56.67	6 th

Source: Field Survey, 2021 *(Multiple response recorded)

Table 3 presents the improved yam technologies used by the respondents in the study area. The improved yam technologies used by the respondents in Enugu State in their order of magnitude include: organic manure (96.67%), improved variety (86.67%), yam seed (66.67%), minisett (65.00%), ware yam (61.67%), inorganic fertilizer (58.33%), herbicide (51.67%) and pesticide (33.33%). On the other hand, the improved yam technologies used by the respondents in Ebonyi State in their order of magnitude include: organic fertilizer (91.67%), inorganic fertilizer (78.33%), minisett (71.67%), improved variety (68.33%), herbicide (66.00%), yam seed (51.67%) and pesticide (23.33%). This result could imply that the most common improved yam technology used in South East Nigeria is organic fertilizer. Increased utilization of organic fertilizer could be attributed to the fact that it is cost effective and safe.

Table 4: The distribution of the respondents according improved yam varieties planted

Indicators	Enugu State (n= 60)			Ebonyi State (n =60)		
	Frequency *	Percentage	Rank	Frequency*	Percentage	Rank
Water yam	51	85.00	1 st	57	95.00	1 st
Yellow yam	38	71.67	2 nd	50	83.33	2 nd
Three leaf yam	27	45.00	5 th	30	50.00	5 th
Aerial yam	40	66.67	3 rd	48	80.00	3 rd
White yam	43	63.33	4 th	45	75.00	4 th

Source: Field Survey, 2021 (Multiple response)

Table 4 presents the improved yam varieties planted by the respondents in the study area. The improved yam varieties planted by the respondents in Enugu State in their order of magnitude include: water yam (85.00%), yellow yam (71.67.33%), Aerial yam (66.67%), white yam (63.33%), and three leaf yam (45.00%). On the other hand, the improved yam planted by the respondents in Ebonyi State in their order of magnitude include: water yam (95.00%), yellow yam (88.33%), Aerial yam (80.00%), white yam (75.00%) and three leaf yam (50.00%). This result could imply that the most common improved yam being planted in South East Nigeria among women are white yam, yellow yam, aerial yam and water yam.

Table 5: Mean rating of the level of participation of women in yam production

Indicators	Enugu State (n= 60)			Ebonyi State (n =60)		
	Total	Mean	Decision	Total	Mean	Decision
Land clearing	123	2.05		142	2.36	
Ridging/mounding	135	2.25		133	2.21	
Planting	182	3.03		205	3.42	
Weeding	216	3.60		212	3.53	
Stalking	191	3.18		131	2.18	
Pest control	196	3.27		197	3.28	
Fertilizer application	211	3.51		192	3.20	
Herbicide application	107	1.78		134	2.23	
Harvesting	146	2.43		176	2.93	
Grand mean		2.79	Accepted		2.82	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2021. Critical mean score = 2.5. Decision rule: Mean \geq 2.5=Accepted while Mean < Rejected. A mean score of 2.5 and above was adjudged very high level, below 1.5 very low level.

Table 5 presents the level of participation of women in yam production in the study area. The grand mean of the level of participation of women in yam production in Enugu State was 2.79 and was accepted because it was greater than the critical mean value of 2.5. On the other hand, the grand mean of the level of participation of women in yam production in Ebonyi State was 2.82 and was accepted because it was greater than the critical mean value of 2.5. This result implies the women in Enugu State and Ebonyi state participated to a very high level in yam production in the area. However, the level of participation of women in Ebonyi State was higher than that of Enugu State. This observation could be a pointer to the fact that women are gaining access to agricultural resources such as land, credit and improved input and are considered to contribute immensely to food security status of their families.

Table 6: The distribution of the respondents according to the constraints in yam production.

Indicators	Enugu State (n= 60)			Ebonyi State (n =60)		
	Frequency*	Percentage	Rank	Frequency*	Percentage	Rank
Lack of land	47	78.33	11 th	50	83.33	9 th
Lack of fertilizer	51	85.00	6 th	56	93.33	4 th
Unavailability of finance	53	88.33	4 th	58	96.67	3 rd
Poor yield	50	83.33	7 th	55	91.67	5 th
Poor access to credit	54	90.00	3 rd	60	100.00	1 st
High cost of labour	49	81.67	9 th	40	66.67	12 th
High cost of equipment	49	81.67	10 th	53	88.33	7 th
Pest and diseases	44	73.33	13 th	50	83.33	10 th
Climate change	58	96.67	2 nd	60	100.00	2 nd
Poor marketing	50	83.33	8 th	54	90.00	6 th
Lack of storage facilities	53	88.33	5 th	51	85.00	8 th
Fragmentation of land	60	100.00	1 st	50	83.33	11 th

Source: Field Survey, 2021 (Multiple response)

Table 6 presents the constraints in yam production and processing in the study area. The most common constraints to yam production and processing in Enugu State in their order of magnitude include: fragmentation of land (100.00%), Climate change (96.67%), poor access to credit (90.00%), unavailability of finance and storage facilities (88.33%) and lack of fertilizer (85.00%). On the other hand, the most common constraints to yam production and processing in Ebonyi State in their order of magnitude include: Poor access to credit and climate change (100.00%), unavailability of finance (96.67%), lack of fertilizer (93.33%), poor yield (91.67%) and poor marketing (90.00%). This finding is in line with Nahanga (2015) who reported that the most common challenges for yam production in Nigeria were climate change and low financial base of the farmers.

Table 7: Regression estimate of the effect of socio economic factors on yam production among women in the study area

Variables	Enugu State +Linear	Ebonyi state +Exponential
Constant	64024.499 (0.995)	-54586.438 (-2.562)**
Age (X ₁)	-1611.993 (-0.798)	-0.257 (-2.060)**
Sex (X ₂)	47433.217 (1.006)	34607.471 (5.488)**
Marital status (X ₃)	-3446.307 (-0.092)	0.328 (1.965)*
Household size(X ₄)	1.206 (3.810)**	-0.186 (-0.522)
Education(X ₅)	1.697 (3.257)**	1.022 (2.927)**
Income(X ₆)	0.636 (4.612)**	0.815 (10.593)**
Farming experience(X ₇)	3275.571 (1.523)	1898.901 (2.727)**
Cooperative membership(X ₈)	-40297.826 (-0.809)	-24050.412 (-0.950)
Farm size(X ₉)	54262.786 (5.660)**	12822.486 (2.512)**
R ²	0.776	0.854
F- ratio	24.449**	32.442**
No	60	60

Source: Field Survey, 2020, Note: +Lead equation, ***1% level of significance, ** 5% level of significance, *10% level of significance, Values in parenthesis are the t-value.

The Ordinary Least Square result of the effect of socio economic factors on yam production. The linear functional form and exponential functional form were chosen as the lead equations. This was based on statistical, economic and econometric reasons which include the magnitude of the coefficient of multiple determination, the number of significant variables. The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) value of 0.776 and (R^2) value of 0.854 which implies that 77.60% and 85.50% of the variations in yam production was explained by the independent variables included in the model (age, sex, marital status, household size, education, income, farming experience, cooperative membership and farm size) while 22.40% and 14.50% unexplained was due to error. F-prob. value of 24.449*** and 32.442** was observed from the analysis which is less than 0.05, indicating that the variables included in the estimated regression model were correct and significant at 1% significant level. However, the significant variables were household size, education, income, farm size, sex, marital status, income, farming experience.

The coefficient of household size, educational status, sex, income and farm size were statistically significant and positively related to yam production among the women at 1% in Enugu state while age, sex, marital status, education, income, farming experience and farm size were statistically significant among women in Ebonyi state. This result implies that a unit increase in any of these variables result to an increase in yam production in the study area. This was expected because large household size may serve as a means of cheap labour for yam production activities among women in the study area. This result is in consonance with Nwaobiala(2018) who noted that relative large household size enhances the availability of labour for increased efficiency among farmers. The coefficient of education was statistically significant and positively related to the yam production among women in the study area at 1%. The implication is that with more education, women are more likely to adopt new technologies and innovations, thereby increasing their level of output level. The result corroborates with that of Abudu, Haruna, Idehen and Janiley (2014) who reported that education positively influence farmers' productivity. Increased in income increases the financial base of the farmers, which in turn facilitates farm expansion. This result agrees with the findings of Umunakwe *et al.*, (2016) as they opined that farm income realized from any farming activity facilitates the purchase of more resources for further production. Farmers operating larger farms tend to have greater financial resources and access to credit to get more involved in yam production activities. This corroborates the findings of Onyenekeet *al.*, (2016) who suggested that farm size influences the level of output of farmers in Nigeria.

The coefficient of age was statistically significant and negatively related to the yam production among women in Ebonyi state at 5%. This result implies that a unit increase in the age of the respondents result to a decrease in the yam production. This finding disagrees with Kadurumba, Njoku and Achi (2019) who reported that age exerted positive effect on the level of output of yam farmers in Ebonyi State. The coefficient of marital status with the value 0.328 was statistically significant and positively related to the yam production at 10%. This implies that any increase in the number of women farmers whom were married will lead to a corresponding increase in yam production. This is expected probably because spouses make effective and better decisions and may have played different roles in yam production activities in the study area. This result is in tandem with Tijani and Audu (2018) who reported a positive relationship between married people and level of output.

CONCLUSION

The level of participation of women in yam production in Enugu and Ebonyi states was high. Even though yam was regarded as men crop. With this finding yam being regarded as men crop in the southeast Nigeria is no longer justifiable. Women participated in every act of yam production in the two states considered in the study Majority of these women yam producers were between the ages of 30...59 years still in their active age and most of them were married. Their level of awareness of improved yam production technologies was also very high in the States. The most common improved yam technology used by the respondents was organic manure. The improved yam varieties planted by the respondents in their order of magnitude included: water yam, yellow yam, aerial yam, white yam and three leaf yam. The major constraints to women participation in yam production in the study area included: poor access to credit, climate change, unavailability of fund, lack of fertilizer, poor yield and poor market. The following variables were significantly related to yam production in the study, household size, education, income, farm size, sex, marital status, income and farming experience.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

Our leaders should aim at solving the major constraints of farmers especially by facilitating access to loans to aid production

Making needed inputs available in time and at subsidized rate is highly recommended.

Deployment of experienced extension workers to aid the farmers with professional advice for increased productivity is needed.

The extension agents should intimate the farmers on effective coping strategies for climate change, as this will help to mitigate the effects on yam production.

Women should try to form farmers' cooperative to make it easier to access credit from donor bodies.

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